

POSITIVE ASPECTS OF APPLICATION OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY

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Annotation: *This article provides information on where and how to use pedagogical technologies in education and their results, their appropriate use in explaining a new topic and strengthening the previous topic.*

Keywords: *technology, International Science Olympiads, modern pedagogical technologies, personality in education, education system.*

Today there are many changes in education. There is a growing interest in education among young people. The number of our spiritually rich and educated youth is growing day by day. This is the result of our country's focus on the future of young people, and especially on education.

The fact that education is person-centered, a new approach not only to the forms and methods of teaching chemistry, but also to its content, has led to great achievements in the field of education. This is evidenced by the fact that in recent years, our young chemist students have won a number of prestigious places in the International Chemistry Olympiads. These achievements are a source of pride for chemistry teachers, as well as a great responsibility. The use of various types of pedagogical technologies during the lessons not only increases the effectiveness of the lesson, but also increases the quality of students' knowledge and interest in science. [1]

There is currently no need to comment on the concepts of 'Technology' or 'Pedagogical Technology' as they have been sufficiently clarified by most scholars. Although the number of educational technologies has increased significantly, the need for newer modern pedagogical technologies is growing and the scope of scientific and pedagogical research on them is expanding.

The main reasons for this are:

- The need for a deeper consideration and use of psychophysiological and personal characteristics of the student;
- The need to further improve the effectiveness of independent work based on the program knowledge, imagination and skills of the student or student;
- The need to strengthen the interest of students in scientific thinking, science, deepen their professional knowledge, increase their activity during theoretical and practical training;
- Recognition of the need to replace the proactive approach;

The current education system in Uzbekistan has sufficient opportunities to organize the learning process, which provides guaranteed learning outcomes and forms the relationship between teacher and student;

In particular, the technology of "Problem" leads students to think, research, work on how to apply the technology in the classroom. [2]

The purpose of technology is to teach students to find the right solution to various problems or situations arising from the subject of the subject, to acquaint them with some methods of problem solving and to choose the appropriate methods for solving the problem. Training is to teach the correct identification of the causes of the problem and the actions to solve the problem.

The order of the lesson is as follows: the teacher divides the students into groups and after placing them in the appropriate places, explains the rules and requirements of the lesson, that is, he conducts the lesson. and that each stage requires maximum attention from the students, and that they work individually, in groups, and as a team during the session. This mood helps students to be ready to complete the tasks assigned to them and stimulates interest. Once the training procedures and requirements are explained, the training will begin.

Carefully watch the film prepared by the students for the lesson and try to identify the problem covered in it, memorize it or mark it in their notebooks (if it is not possible to show the film, then the teacher should read it. a poster, a picture, a poster, or a text describing a problem on the topic of the subject, may use the study material in the book);

- Writes the problems identified by each group member from this sheet (picture, text, life event) with a felt-tip pen on Whatman or A-4 format paper;
- At the end of the allotted time, the prepared work will be read by a representative of the group;

-distributed to the groups by replacing the papers selected by the teacher groups and with the problems;

- Each member of the group chooses one of the problems of interest from the problems written by the groups in the handouts;

- Independently analyzes the problem selected by each group member in the following diagram distributed by the teacher.

For example:

The problem type	Causes of the problem	Ways to solve the problem and your actions
Lack of clean drinking water	Lack of focus on keeping water clean	Concerning nature and water conservation holding events

Lack of attention to water conservation is related to nature and water conservation holding events

- At the end of the individual activity, each student reads out the results of the analysis;

- collective exchange of views on problems and their solutions;

The small groups are thanked for their fun work and given homework. "Think, search and find!" The method is very useful for strengthening the topic. [3]

Complete the assignment.

Identify the names of substances that have the following structure and the type of chemical bonds in them, hybridization.

Molecules	Types of chemical bonds	Types of hybrids

 XeF ₄		
 XeF ₆		
 XeO ₃		
 XeO ₄		
 XeOF ₂		
 XeO ₃ F ₂		
 XeOF ₄		

Complete the assignment.

Crystal lattices	What kind of substance and the type of chemical bond	hybridization

Complete the assignment.

Electronic clouds	How to connect and hybrids	Give specific examples
<p>(b)</p>		

As a result of training with such technologies, students learn that before solving a problem, they must first determine the cause, and then understand the methods and techniques they need, and clearly define their actions.

One of the most important tasks of a teacher is to teach students innovative lessons, to prepare lessons based on new pedagogical technologies, to convey them to students, to listen to their opinions, to communicate with them, to motivate students, to form their interest in science. It is necessary. [5]

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